

EMERGING COMPOSITION: BEING AND BECOMING

AN EXPERIMENT IN PROGRESS

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ABSTRACT

Emerging Composition: Being and Becoming envisions a work in continuous transformation, never reaching an equilibrium, a complex dynamic system whose components permanently fluctuate and adjust to global changes. The process never produces a definitive version, but provides at any arbitrary point in time a plausible variant of the work - a transitory being. Directed Graphs are used to represent the structural levels of a composition (vertices) and the relationships between them (edges); parent-children and ancestor-descendant type connections describe well potential hierarchies in a piece of music. By determining adjacencies and degrees of vertices and introducing weights for edges, one can define affinities and dependencies in the complex and flexible structure that is a musical composition. Ways in which the all-incidence matrix of a graph with weighted edges can evolve are discussed including the use for that purpose of elements of Information Theory. The Emerging Composition model is closer to the way composers actually write music and refine their output; it also creates the equivalent of a live organism, growing, developing, and transforming itself over time.

1. BACKGROUND

The process of writing a new piece involves balancing elements that belong to different structural levels from the overall form of the composition to various sound characteristics. Composer Aurel Stroe and his collaborators discussed in the article “Morphogenetic Music” [1] the play between melody, rhythm, harmony, and phrase length in Mozart's *Piano Sonata in C Major K.W. 309* showing how unexpected or more daring choices at one structural level are compensated by blander, more familiar occurrences at others. A related insight into the composition process is given by Beethoven's sketchbooks that show a constant adjustment, sometimes over years, of initial motives [2] and by the works of Charles Ives who continued to modify his music even after it was published.

These universal concerns also apply to contemporary works and are shared by artists regardless of aesthetics, historical moment or style. Today, in electro-acoustic music, readily available software allows authors to easily investigate alternatives in placing and replacing gestures, textures, structural elements, etc. or even to further adapt

and polish the sound materials after the completion of the project.

1.1 Manifold Compositions

When a computer-generated piece contains elements of indeterminacy, multiple variants can be produced simply by changing the initial conditions (eg. the random number generator's seed). Randomness may be involved in selecting the order of macro and micro events, in the choice of attack times and durations of sounds, of their frequencies, amplitudes, spectra, etc. or of their environment's properties such as location in space and reverberation. Such multiple variants, members of a *manifold composition*, have exactly the same structure and are the result of precisely the same process but differ in the way individual events with their diverse characteristics are distributed in time: like faces in a crowd, they all share basic features but exhibit particular attributes. A *manifold composition* is an equivalence class, a composition class, produced by a computer under particular conditions [3]. It includes all its actual and virtual variants and requires that all of them be equally acceptable. *Manifold compositions* build on the example of Stockhausen (*Plus-minus*) [4], Xenakis (*ST* pieces) [5] and Michael Gottfried Koenig (*Segmente*) [6] and extend it: by stipulating the use of a computer and introducing an element of indeterminacy during the act of composing in the case of Stockhausen; by adding more constraints in the last two cases.

1.2 DISSCO

The software used in the production of *manifolds*, a Digital Instrument for Sound Synthesis and Composition, DISSCO [7], provides a seamless approach to composition and sound design. An integrated environment, it has three major parts: LASS, a Library for Additive Sound Synthesis, which builds sounds from first principles (sine waves), CMOD, or Composition MODule, a collection of methods for composition that drives the synthesis engine, and LASSIE, a graphic user interface (GUI).

DISSCO is comprehensive in the sense that it does not require the intervention of the user once it begins to run. This kind of “black box” set of instructions is necessary for preserving the integrity of *manifold* production: intervening during computations or modifying the output would amount to the alteration of the data or of the logic

embedded in the software. Due to a LASS option not available on other systems, the precise control of the *perceived loudness* - a non-linear function of amplitude [8], post-production interventions become not only unnecessary but also incongruent with the purpose of the enterprise.

1.3 Indeterminacy

Randomness in DISSCO is introduced through simple uniform (flat) distributions by the RANDOM and RANDOMINT methods or made available through envelopes, functions of time (in most cases) built by the user. An envelope library, ENVLIB allows the composer to draw the contour of the curve, scale and store it while MAKE ENVELOPE offers not only the possibility to enter a list of x and y values but also to specify a range within which each of them may randomly fluctuate. Stochastic distributions expressions are handled through *muparser* [9], downloaded from the web and now part of DISSCO.

Two alternative options are introduced by STOCHOS: 1) a dynamic range whose min. and Max. limits are defined by two functions/envelopes while a third one controls the distribution of elements within the confined area and 2) multiple probability ranges whose sum is 1 at any moment (inspired by Xenakis' special density diagram determining orchestral composition)[10]. Finally, VALUEPICK, connected to SIEVE, introduces weighted probabilities assigned to discrete values at any parameter.

One of the underlying ideas behind CMOD is that when choosing concrete values from frequency and spectra to the formal design of a work, the same type of operations are used at different time scales. All these methods are considered “utilities” available in a multitude of situations.

2. DIRECTED GRAPHS

The structure of CMOD can be represented as a directed graph (DG), a *rooted tree*, where every structural level inherits from a generic Event class in a *matryoshka* type of arrangement: a unique Top event (the root) can include High events followed by Mid, Low, and Bottom events - the platform where individual sounds are created. In this model, events are represented as vertices each of them having siblings (except the root) and spawning any number of children. They are connected by edges that illustrate the relationships between them. By carefully determining adjacencies and degrees of all vertices and by introducing weights for edges, one can start defining affinities and dependencies in the complex and flexible structure that is a musical composition. The scheme can accommodate both the stricter order found in traditional music (piece < sections < themes < motives < cells < sounds), and, at the other extreme, if only the root and its immediate children are present, random distribution of undifferentiated events within the confines of the piece (sounds in Cage's chance music works). Moreover, this model is well suited to create “floating hierarchies”, unstable flows of information that favor change over established formulations [11].

Figure 1. DISSCO structure as a rooted directed graph. For clarity only one intermediate level (M) is shown.

2.1 Similar Approaches

It should be noted that Pierre Barbaud had explored the use of graphs in “automatizing” the production of tonal harmonic and contrapuntal sequences in his own compositions as early as the 1960s [12] and that there is a similarity between DGs and the arborescences on which many later works of Xenakis are predicated. More recently, a number of authors have either proposed musical formalisms and/or built systems based on Directed Graphs. Among them, *Nodal* a system for generative composition [13] and *Graph Theory*, a piece by Jason Freeman [14] are the closer to the tenor of this project.

At the present time, Emerging Composition project adopts the point of view that one way in which any musical composition and its structural levels can be described is as a rooted tree DG. It is a framework that corresponds *post factum* to the way CMOD was organized, a starting point informed by musical practice. Not intended as a way to generate pitches, rhythms, etc. or to explore the limits of creativity like other schemes, it is used to represent relations between structural components of a musical work - a rather limited goal for this phase of the project that could be expanded in the future.

Relevant to possible future developments is Jonathan Owen Clark's formalism exposed in *Nonlinear Dynamic of Networks* [15] that brings together Graphs and Dynamic Systems. It could be applied to the content of vertices - sounds in a multidimensional vector space - and to their influence on the macro levels of a piece.

3. COMPLEX DYNAMIC SYSTEMS

Any composition can be thought of as a complex system. During the process of composing it, the system is also dynamic in the sense that options are re-evaluated at various times leading to changes both in the macro structure and in the details of the work. It should also be pointed out that, although complex dynamic systems are often assumed to be chaotic, that is not necessarily the case.

The Evolving Composition project models such a dynamic system by allowing the computations to continue for an arbitrary amount of time. It envisions a work in perpetual transformation, never reaching an equilibrium, a complex structure whose components permanently fluctuate and adjust to each other's modifications - a "brewing" piece. Such a composition can be regarded as a network of evolving interdependent elements whose alterations, refinements, and transformations create a series of unstable states. It could be likened to an electric grid where power is generated, routed, and distributed through different nodes: a network of diverse but interdependent components. The grid has to be responsive and to constantly adjust the flow of electricity to compensate for surges in demand or for local failures. Its musical equivalent is a composition whose parts are interconnected at all levels in such a way that modifying one component could have global consequences and affect other parts of the system.

This view of the composition as a network of perpetually unfolding elements in search of an elusive balance, similar to a living creature, epitomizes an "organic" approach to creating music. The process never produces a definitive version but provides at any arbitrary point in time a plausible variant of the work - a transitory being.

Emerging Composition: Being and Becoming is an augmentation and a corollary of the *manifold* idea as they both generate an unlimited number of variants, involve the presence of randomness at all structural levels, and relay on the view of sounds as events in a multidimensional vector space whose degrees of freedom include time/duration, frequency, amplitude, phase, etc. The project adopts the view that a composition could be represented as a hierarchical structure (but does not have to) and that it is predicated on discovering and creating new situations as opposed to attaining known, already established goals: a volatile, temporary equilibrium and NOT a search for a stable optimal solution.

4. THE DESIGN

4.1 Trivial Case

Upon finishing a new piece, a human composer might step back, take a fresh look at the work and, possibly, decide to make changes and adjustments. The Emerging Composition allows computations to continue after the first variant of the *manifold* is completed: a new edge is created between the last Bottom event \mathbf{X}_{last} , (a terminal vertex) and another vertex \mathbf{X}_{new} which could be a sibling, a parent or an ancestor belonging to the same branch or to a different one. The operation takes place with the help of an all-incidence matrix \mathcal{M} of the type shown in Figure 2.

This transitional matrix is weighted (expressing probabilities of exploring different edges) and serves as a template for the Evolving Entity, a sort of genome of the composition.

The selection of \mathbf{X}_{new} involves dividing the components of the vector \mathbf{V}_{last} (corresponding to \mathbf{X}_{last}) by their sum, adding the results in order from the top to bottom,

with 1 in the last row, and matching a random number to one of the probability intervals thus created. If the newly chosen vertex \mathbf{X}_{new} is a parent, all its descendents are computed anew. Upon completion an audio file becomes available for examination (or ignored) and a vector \mathbf{V}_{new} corresponding to the chosen vertex \mathbf{X}_{new} is used to continue. The procedure may be repeated an arbitrary number of times.

	T	M ₀	M ₁	B ₀	B ₁	B ₂	B ₃	B ₄
T	0.01	0.05	0.05	0.02	0.01	0.03	0.03	0.01
M ₀	0.20	0.01	0.25	0.20	0.20	0.05	0.10	0.07
M ₁	0.20	0.01	0.01	0.11	0.10	0.25	0.20	0.23
B ₀	0.12	0.20	0.11	0.01	0.30	0.19	0.08	0.07
B ₁	0.12	0.24	0.10	0.35	0.01	0.07	0.08	0.09
B ₂	0.12	0.06	0.15	0.10	0.12	0.01	0.26	0.26
B ₃	0.12	0.08	0.18	0.11	0.14	0.25	0.01	0.26
B ₄	0.11	0.06	0.15	0.11	0.12	0.25	0.24	0.01

Figure 2. All-incidence weighted matrix

4.2 Continuity

If the process of re-evaluating vertices proceeds without interruption, the continuous sequence of pseudorandom numbers creates a history uniquely determined by the seed state and its integrity confers to the Emerging Composition Entity in question the equivalent of a perennial "personality", an identity and a "individual history". There is a paradox here: the choices leading to any given variant of the manifold depend on chance but the random numbers themselves are part of a causal, deterministic chain. Combined with the fact that the directed graph and the matrix - the genome - are pre-determined, a balance is created between Being/structure, and Becoming/indeterminacy, and the piece starts to resemble a living organism whose cells are rejuvenated constantly while the creature endures.

4.3 Template Modification

Modifications of the template/genome may be introduced as the computations continue. If the column vector representing the last choice \mathbf{V}_{last} is multiplied by the matrix \mathcal{M} , $\mathbf{V}_{\text{last}} * \mathcal{M}$, a Markov chain mechanism is initiated and the newly resulting vector $\mathbf{V}_{\text{last}+1}$ becomes part of an ordered sequence of causally connected vectors. This operation is repeated every time a new variant of the piece completes. In most cases the root of the tree, the piece itself, is not affected; however, that might change if the total duration of the entire piece is allowed to fluctuate between certain limits using one of the methods outlined in 1.3.

The user controls the likelihood of various connections/edges between vertices through the static, all-incidence matrix \mathcal{M} . The Markov chain mechanism described above allows a vector to evolve in a predictable way but assumes that the content of the other vector/columns of the matrix remain the same. A more realistic alternative is to take into account global changes that might occur

every time a new version is computed - something a human composer would probably do.

Such adjustments are construed as the result of the composer's intuition, taste, training, etc. but many times these subjective considerations can also be described using elements of Information Theory. The main concepts provided by Information Theory as applied to musical messages are those of Entropy/Order - expressed through the relationship between Originality and Redundancy, a dialectical opposition - in relation to the Complexity of the work [8]. Their relevance to this project is based on at least two facts: these are measurable quantities and, as Herbert Brün once put it: "the job of a composer is to delay the decay of information".

As an example, Originality may be equated with *im*-probability hence with the delivered Information, Redundancy with repetition and/or familiarity, and Complexity with the number of available choices, all quantifiable if not entirely in an objective way. Since each variant of the piece exhibits new, different values for most vertices, an analysis of all values at all vertices followed by a comparison with a desired (dynamic) situation becomes necessary. In turn, such an extensive re-evaluation of data requires a significant increase in computing time and storage capacity since even a relatively short work may easily contain hundreds of vertices.

Moreover, the vertices representing the Bottom level contain significantly more information than those corresponding to higher level vertices and are more likely to trigger more often global changes. This is because sound design procedures are concentrated at the Bottom level: various ways of assigning the frequency and loudness of a sound, the rate and amplitude of vibrato (FM), of tremolo (AM) or of frequency and amplitude transients. Information about spatialization and reverberation should also be added to the list.

4.3 Developing Entity

The Complex Dynamic System that is the Emerging Entity/Composition includes the DG rooted tree that is DISSCO, the template/genome matrix \mathcal{M} , and the set of data used to create the initial variant of the piece. The preceding discussion has assumed the size of the rooted tree and, necessarily, that of the matrix, constant. However, the process could start with a tree and a matrix reduced to the smallest possible number of vertices/vectors, for instance only the Top vertex (the piece) and one or two Bottom or terminal vertices. The system is then allowed to grow, developing more edges and vertices at a rate controlled by the user until reaching its maximum potential. The opposite, a decaying slope can be engineered by cutting off branches of the tree and reducing gradually the size of the matrix. In the end, a restricted number of vertices and edges containing a smaller and smaller number of possible choices or a situation similar to reaching the ergodic (stationary) state of a Markov chain could signify the demise of the Entity/Composition. Using another analogy with biological processes, the growing number of

vertices and edges in the beginning part of its evolution mirrored by a reduction of the network toward the end could be associated with the growing during the first years of human existence of the number of neurons and synapses and then the pruning that occurs during adolescence.

5. IMPLEMENTATION

5.1 Why DISSCO ?

Emerging Composition uses the structure and features of DISSCO, a powerful application that has been proven reliable and robust during an almost a decade of use. It also benefits from the experience accumulated both by seasoned users and by students in the classroom. DISSCO offers an unbroken link between a Computer-assisted (Algorithmic) Composition module that offers deterministic tools (patterns, sieves, etc.) along random distributions and a synthesis engine with uncommon capabilities (control of perceived loudness, polar coordinates, etc.) that generates - according to users - a sound output superior to many other similar applications. Combining complex designing abilities with a sophisticated artisanal proficiency and being an extension of the *manifold* undertaking, DISSCO constitutes the best choice available.

5.2 Present phase

After considering a number of alternatives, the general framework described above was selected. The Trivial Case was implemented by connecting the last Bottom event, a terminal vertex, to the Top event without interrupting the sequence of random numbers. This first stage of the project is used to generate *Sound Fountain*, an installation generating continuous sound output in the atrium of a local modern building.

Presently, the Emerging Composition project runs in multithreading mode and has been recently ported on a multi-core system. Using 16 CPU cores when producing a complex eight channel piece, the ratio between computation time and the duration of the piece (real time) is a little less than 3/2 and increasing the number of cores does not result in a significant improvement. In other examples, a six minute stereo piece ran on the same system in less than five minutes while an experiment in granular synthesis, also done with DISSCO, of over 350,000 grains with dozens of partials each, took over five hours.

Computing time depends heavily on both the complexity of individual sounds and their individual duration. DISSCO was conceived as a "Rolls Royce bulldozer" (refined control over large numbers of elements) running on high-performance computers: it allows for an arbitrary number of partials and envelope segments along with involved selections of sound attributes. However, a meaningful functioning of the system requires a ratio of 1/1 or better and a urgent task is to profile, optimize, and parallelize the code in order to constantly achieve real time or faster.

5.3 Future work

As mentioned in the title, this is an experiment in progress and it is in its incipient stage. As previously described, a general plan has been formulated but many theoretical and practical aspects still need to be worked out.

Conceptually, the project is situated at the intersection of Dynamical Systems Theory, Graph Theory, and Information Theory and a link between them which is both solid and practical still needs to be formulated.

From a computational point of view, meaningful ways of creating the M matrix need to be explored. As an example, a recent work can be represented by a rooted tree containing 132 discrete vertices (event types). A 132×132 matrix or even matrices an order of magnitude higher are manageable but they will have to be constantly updated and various operations performed on them. In the case elements of Information Theory are used, an analysis of each new variant of the piece is necessary which means information for 15,700 sounds (as in the example mentioned) or more will have to be not only stored but also analyzed. Hence, the need for high-performance computing – at least at the present time.

6. CONCLUSIONS

Emerging Composition: Being and Becoming creates an original paradigm within the field of Computer-assisted (Algorithmic) Composition. Although the concepts of Complex Dynamic Systems and Graph Theory have been discussed in connection with Catastrophe Theory and Morphogenetic Music by Stroe [1] and by Clark [15] in the context of (pseudo-)tonal music [17], to our knowledge, there have been no proposals for building a concrete mechanism in order to generate a continuously evolving composition, resulting from uninterrupted computations.

This paradigm has the potential for further significant developments beyond the immediate scope of this project such as creating an “ecosystem” where the performance environment (hall acoustics) and live performers' decisions influence the composition - along the lines envisioned by Agostino Di Scipio [18].

6.1 Responding to well defined needs

The system described here responds to the needs of a personal creative project meant to expand the *manifold* undertaking. No other available software was deemed appropriate and, although its origins are idiosyncratic, it is maturing into a considerably more general tool. It creates pieces *in toto*, not piece-meal, preserving their identity in the case of *manifold* variants and insuring the continuity of the Evolving Entity through multiple generations. This is possible due to the unbroken flow between composition and synthesis merged into a unique smooth process that also insures total control of sound design details.

Similar to the *manifolds*, the system is based on the solid foundation provided by the description of sounds as events in a multidimensional vector space and it creates a

general framework that can accommodate different aesthetics not just one particular style.

6.2 Pushing boundaries

Akin to some of the contributions already mentioned, this approach elevates the understanding of composition and composing to an abstract level and bridges the separation between music and other domains through the use of mathematical tools and by requiring state of the art, high-performance computing.

The Emerging Entity composition model is closer to how humans actually compose, by trial and error, continuously refining the output: it better approximates the workings of the human mind. It also reflects the natural world by creating (like some Artificial Life projects) the equivalent of a live organism, growing, developing, transforming itself over time and thus fulfilling the goal expressed by John Cage: “to imitate nature in its mode of operation”.

In the process, it changes the role of the composer from artisan (making distinctive products in small quantities and using **traditional** methods) to that of a *Demiourgos* who creates from scratch (ie. using additive synthesis) multiple life-like Entities.

Emerging Composition and *manifold compositions* represent an idiomatic way of using computers in music by mass spawning unique versions of the same archetype. A provision already present in the production of *manifolds* requires that a version of the output can not be performed in public more than once; presenting the piece as it exists only at one instance of a continuous process, an aspect of it which will be never repeated, stresses the ephemeral quality of any activity and prevents the piece to become a commodity. By questioning the uniqueness of the musical object - the piece - the proposal falls under the category of experimental music driven by speculative inclinations.

It also becomes the reflection of a particular worldview that contemplates the relationships between determinism/causality and randomness, between static templates and unforeseen particular events, between Being and Becoming. Or, in different words, it expresses the tension between the search for order and meaning and what Camus called the “silence of an indifferent universe”.

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